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Name: Daniel Sander

Organisation: Federal Highway Research Institute (BAST)

E-Mail address: sander@bast.de

DETECTING LATENT RELATIONS WITHIN IN-DEPTH ACCIDENT DATA USING NETWORK GRAPHS

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SUMMARY

Accident data analysis is critical for understanding the complex interactions between contributing factors and developing effective strategies to reduce road accidents and fatalities. In this study, the use of network graphs as a tool to visualize relationships in accident data was explored to identify latent connections that may not be directly noticed through traditional data analysis methods. A subsample of the GIDAS database was used to generate three network graphs based on keywords extracted from the accident information. For each graph, either the Jaccard similarity, an adapted version of the Jaccard similarity or the cosine similarity was used for weighting the connection between keywords. In combination with a local filtering procedure, this led to diverging visualizations highlighting different connections of accident characteristics.

The findings indicate that network graphs are a valuable and effective approach for visually mapping the intricate relationships among various contributing factors in accident data. The graphical representation of these relationships facilitates the quick identification of potential connections, aiding in the formulation of testable hypotheses for further validation through established statistical methods. The credibility of the connections depicted in the graph was assessed using traditional descriptive methods, using the keyword "alcohol" as an example. This analysis substantiated that the apparent connections to keywords related to accident type, accident cause, and time of day are statistically significant. Also, the limitations of the approach, such as the specificity of force-directed spatialization and the need for careful consideration of the weighting method used, are discussed.

In conclusion, the use of network graphs in accident data analysis holds promise in providing insights into latent relationships and supporting the development of effective strategies for accident prevention.

1. INTRODUCTION

The vision of the EU's road safety policy "Vizion Zero" is to reduce the number of road fatalities to zero by 2050 (European Commission, 2020). From the perspective of vehicle safety, a measure to reach this long-term goal is the introduction and amendment of regulations that oblige manufacturers to install state-of-the-art safety systems into their vehicles. For example, the evaluation of Regulation (EU) No 347/2012, which obliged manufacturers to equip their trucks and busses with AEBS, shows a clear decrease in the number of accidents and injury severity for rear-end collisions on German motorways (Straßgütl and Sander, 2021).

To evaluate and prioritize what measures are relevant for traffic and vehicle safety, policymakers and consumer protection consult accident statistics. Accident data is aggregated in a variety of accident databases, covering different regions and levels of detail, such as high-level data from CARE (European Commission, 2021) and national statistics and in-depth data from databases like GIDAS (Liers, 2018) and IGLAD (Bakker et al., 2017).

Analysing this data is a crucial step in understanding traffic accidents and developing strategies to prevent them. By visualizing the relationships between different contributing factors, such as the type of accident, the type of vehicle, or the surrounding environment, and by identifying relationships in the data, researchers and policymakers can gain a deeper understanding of the underlying causes of traffic accidents and develop more effective interventions and regulations.

Latent relations refer to relationships or connections in data that are not directly observable or immediately apparent. They are underlying patterns or associations that can be revealed through different analysis methods. One method that has been extensively utilized in a variety of fields, including computer and social sciences, as well as transportation and others is network theory and analysis. Especially in social sciences and emerging online social networks graph theory and network graphs are widely used tools for analysing the relationships of the elements involved (Gamper, 2022; Eom and Jo, 2014).

Adapting this approach to accident data could offer the advantage of providing a simple visual representation of the relationships between variables that can then be further and specifically analysed through established statistical methods. A further use case is to uncover latent relationships that may exist between various contributing factors to traffic accidents. Network graph-based analysis of accident data has been performed by Zhang et al. (2022). They constructed a knowledge graph based on structured traffic accident case data. Based on this knowledge graph, they performed multidimensional and multilevel analysis utilizing the Neo4j graph database with the associated Cypher query language for retrieving data. The analysis was carried out regarding

accident portraits, accident classification, accident statistics, and accident association path (Zhang et al., 2022).

Kwayu et al. (2021) used crash narratives and crash metadata to understand persistent crash factors and the co-occurrence of factors that contribute to crash incidents. The authors used the structural topic modelling (STM) approach and network topology analysis to investigate fatal crash narratives from the online crash database, Michigan Traffic Crash Facts (MTCF). The network topology was applied to study the connection between topics derived from crash narratives, which describe the details of the crash event, the location, and the parties involved. As a result, network graphs were generated for various crash types and driver age groups (Kwayu et al., 2021).

Lin et al. (2014) explored the use of a modularity-optimizing community detection algorithm and an association rule learning algorithm to identify important accident characteristics. The authors applied the algorithms to a network graph based on an accident data set from the Buffalo-Niagara Metropolitan area in New York. They used the community detection algorithm to cluster the data and reduce heterogeneity. The association rule learning algorithm was then applied to each cluster to discover meaningful patterns related to high accident frequency locations and incident clearance time (Lin et al., 2014).

Given that human beings tend to process information to a great extent through visual perception (Grady et al., 1998), this study aims to explore the potential of network graphs as a means to visually represent connections in accident data. The research question to be answered is therefore: are network graphs a suitable tool to study the interconnection of accident characteristics and in this way uncover latent relationships? Thus, the objective is to create a network graph based on accident data and to investigate the connection between accident characteristics. In contrast to previous work, connections between accident characteristics are not to be highlighted by complex analysis procedures, but by suitable visualisation using the graphs structures. Meeting the objective would allow a more targeted analysis of road safety risks using established methods.

This paper is organized as follows: The method utilized for producing network graphs is presented in the first section. It encompasses a comprehensive examination of the dataset utilized, the creation of keywords that act as nodes, and the computation of interconnection strength. The subsequent section displays the resulting network graphs, and a select number of connections are verified against exploratory data analysis techniques to assess the credibility of the connections and graph configurations. Finally, the suitability of using network graphs to visualize accident data is critically evaluated in the last section.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The following section describes the method that was used to generate network graphs using the data collected in the German In-Depth Accident Study (GIDAS).

2.1. GIDAS DATABASE

GIDAS is a cooperative project between the German Federal Highway Research Institute and the Research Association for Automotive Technology for collecting detailed accident data involving at least one injured person. Every year, around 1000 to 2000 traffic accidents are recorded by specialized teams in a two-stage sampling procedure in the greater region of Dresden and – except for the years 2020-2022 – the greater Hanover region (Pfeiffer and Schmidt, 2012). The investigation takes place “on scene” and “in time”, meaning that the data collection starts immediately on the accident site. There the teams collect data independently from the police, take photos, and interrogate participants and witnesses. Further data is collected in later stages by visiting the hospital (medical data), the scrap yard (vehicle data), or the laboratory for accident reconstruction. In the end, an accident is described in detail by about 3500 parameters and 150-170 photos (Liers, 2018). The data is stored in the GIDAS accident database in relational form. For this survey, the July 2021 version of the database is used, which includes 42310 accidents.

Variable sample

This study focuses on a subset of the GIDAS database to minimize computational requirements and ensure data quality. The analysis is limited to relatively recent accidents occurring between 2015 and 2021 that have been fully reconstructed. To create a concise structure of the network graph while maintaining a holistic representation of accidents, a sample of representative variables for four superordinate categories of accident characteristics, as defined by Eboli et al. (2020) was chosen: contextual factors, vehicle-related factors, participant-related factors, and road-related factors. The resulting sample includes 47 variables.

2.2. THE PROCESS TO GENERATE THE NETWORK GRAPH

A graph models and visualizes relationships between entities, with each entity represented as a node n_i in a set of nodes N . An edge is created when two nodes are paired, with the connection denoted as (n_1, n_2) and the set of edges represented as E . A graph can be generally written in the form $G = (N, E)$ and is either directed or undirected (Metcalf and Casey, 2016). Keywords that describe the accident are representing the graph's nodes. The interconnection between the keywords is calculated by using different similarity measures. These interconnections (represented as edges) are mutual and therefore result in an undirected graph. When comparing different similarity measures, this leads to a variance in the number of edges due to local filtering. For an accident a_1 in the set of accidents A , the set of keywords could look like $K_1 = \{\text{"day", "rain", "motorized two-wheeler", "frontal collision", \dots}\}$.

Preprocessing

The sample used from the GIDAS database contains 11107 accidents. To facilitate the linkage of keywords in a subsequent stage, the relational representation of the data was transformed into an object-oriented representation. This involved creating an object with attributes equivalent to the original variables for each accident. The variable characteristics were subsequently assigned as values to the attributes of the accident object. Through this process, the data, which was originally in numeric code, has been translated into the corresponding label texts. If the numeric code describes a scalar value, a grouping is performed as translation. Thus, for the number of parties involved, a grouping into single-vehicle or multi-vehicle accidents takes place. The vehicle age at the time of the accident and the initial speed are also classified. The object generation procedure was also applied to the creation of participant and person objects, which were subsequently linked to their respective accidents as subordinate objects.

Since the input of accident-relevant data into the GIDAS database is largely done manually by the survey teams, errors in coding, invalid codes or missing values may occur due to missing information or input errors. While incorrect data can only be avoided in the data entry process by the survey teams, incomplete data is detected during the translation process of the codes into the respective labels. Accordingly, no keyword can be generated based on these attributes. Consequently, the final graph could be biased and should be checked against established data

analysis methods where the percentage of missing data is indicated. However, the portion of missing information in the variable set is below 0.05 % and since the purpose of the network graphs is to quickly generate hypotheses for further analysis, established data analysis methods needs to be incorporated in a later stage anyway.

Keywords are generated by running through the accident objects one after the other. The values of the attributes of accident, participant, and person objects are transferred into a common set of keywords. Each keyword is used only once per set so that duplicates are filtered out. Thus, for each accident a_i of the total set of all accidents A , a set of keywords K_i is generated. *Fig. 1* shows an example of how accident, participant and person objects are structured and what a set of keywords might look like.

Fig. 1: Example of how an accident object is structured with its sub-objects and how a keyword set is generated using the object's attribute values.

Calculation of edge weights

In the context of the study, the edge weight represents the strength of the relationship between two keywords. This is equivalent to the dependence and the importance of the keywords to each other. If the edge weight between two nodes is greater than 0, these nodes are connected with an edge. In total, three graphs are generated whose edge weights are calculated with one of the similarity measures Jaccard coefficient (JC), adapted Jaccard coefficient (AJC), or cosine similarity (CS).

Jaccard similarity coefficient

The Jaccard similarity coefficient is a similarity measure that is commonly used in the context of comparing sets of items. It is defined as the size of the intersection of two sets divided by the size of the union of the two sets. Therefore it is a measure of the percentage overlap of two sets with values between 0 (no overlap) and 1 (complete overlap) (Arnaboldi et al., 2015). In the context of determining the edge weight of a graph that consists of accident keywords, the Jaccard coefficient is used to measure the similarity between two keywords based on the overlap of the set of accidents in which they appear. For two accidents that are described by the keyword sets K_1 and K_2 , the Jaccard similarity coefficient JC is calculated by:

$$JC(K_1, K_2) = \frac{|K_1 \cap K_2|}{|K_1 \cup K_2|}$$

It is important to note that the Jaccard similarity coefficient is sensitive to the total number of sets. So, it is possible that the edge weight between two keywords can change if the number of accidents increases.

Adapted Jaccard similarity coefficient

Since the Jaccard similarity coefficient has the drawback that it tends to penalize sets with a roughly unequal size, an adaption is formulated that takes into account the mutual relationship between keywords. The adaption does not only consider the intersection of the two sets but also the ratio of intersection over both sets. This allows giving more weight to accidents where one keyword is frequently associated with the other keyword but not the reverse. This is useful for analysing a network of keywords, in cases where one keyword is much more relevant to another keyword than the reverse (Kriesel, 2016). For two accidents that are described by the keyword sets K_1 and K_2 , the adapted Jaccard coefficient AJC is calculated by:

$$AJC(K_1, K_2) = \frac{|K_1 \cap K_2|}{|K_1|} + \frac{|K_1 \cap K_2|}{|K_2|}$$

By adding the two ratios, the coefficient can reach values up to 2, so that normalization is performed at the end.

Cosine similarity

The cosine similarity is a measure that quantifies the similarity between two vectors of an inner product space. It is calculated as the cosine of the angle between vectors, and it provides an indication of how closely aligned the vectors are. This similarity metric is commonly employed in text analysis to evaluate the similarity between documents (Han et al., 2012). A value of 0 means that the two vectors are orthogonal to each other and therefore do not share any similarities. The

closer the values tend toward 1, the more similar the vectors are to each other. To calculate the cosine similarity and use it as a measure for the edge weight, a keyword-accident matrix is created where the rows represent the keywords and the columns represent the accidents. Each entry in the matrix indicates whether the keyword is related to the accident (value 1) or not (value 0). Thus, to determine the similarity of two keywords, the angle between their respective row vectors is calculated. The cosine similarity CS is calculated between row vectors as:

$$CS = \frac{X \cdot Y}{\|X\| \|Y\|}$$

Where X and Y are row vectors of the keyword-accident matrix and $\|X\|$, $\|Y\|$ the corresponding magnitude.

Comparing similarity measures

For each of the three similarity measures, a network graph was generated from the keywords. With the Root Mean Squared Deviation (RMSD) the difference between the edge weights of the three graphs is compared, and an overall measure of the dissimilarity between them is provided. The RMSD method can be used because the graphs have the same structure. This means that the only difference between the three weighting methods is the value of the edge weight and not whether a connection (edge weight > 0) between two nodes is established or not. Formally, given n edges in each graph, the RMSD is defined as:

$$RMSD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (w_{1,i} - w_{2,i})^2}{n}}$$

where $w_{1,i}$ is the weight of the i -th edge in the first graph, $w_{2,i}$ is the weight of the i -th edge in the second graph.

Filter Procedure

Due to the high number of connections between the keywords, the visualization of the graph quickly becomes cluttered. To preserve the basic structure of the graph, but greatly reduce the number of edges, local filtering is used. For each node, the 5 % of the edges with the highest weight are kept or in case the number would round to zero, at least one. This allows for drastically reducing the number of edges and highlights the most important connections between two nodes (keywords). Due to the different calculation methods for the edge weights, the filtering process leads to different graphs in the visualisation.

Graph Layouting

Graph spatialization algorithms are techniques used to layout nodes and edges of a graph in a two-dimensional space. The goal of these algorithms is to visually represent the structure of the graph in a way that is easy to understand and interpret. Force-based techniques are a class of graph spatialization algorithms that use a physical metaphor to layout the nodes and edges of a graph. These techniques simulate the forces that would act on the nodes if they were physical objects.

One of the most popular force-based algorithms is the Fruchterman-Reingold algorithm, which uses a spring-electrostatic model to layout the graph. In this model, each node is treated as a point charge and each edge is treated as a spring (Fruchterman and Reingold, 1991). The strength of the spring, or the attractive force between the nodes, is determined by the edge weight. The algorithm then simulates the physical interactions between the repulsive charges and attractive springs to determine the final layout of the graph. ForceAtlas2 is a further developed force-based algorithm, that weakens the repulsion force between a poorly connected node and a very connected one, to bring them closer to each other (Jacomy et al., 2014).

For visualisation, the software Gephi is used. Gephi is an open-source software for visualising and analysing large networks and complex systems (Bastian et al., 2009). It provides a wide range of network visualization and analysis features, including the implementation of the network spatialization algorithm ForceAtlas2, which is used to generate the layout of the graphs.

Node Size

In graph visualization, the size of the nodes can convey information about the relative importance of the nodes in the network. One common metric used to quantify the importance of a node is the eigenvector centrality, which not only takes into account the number of connections of a node, but also the centrality, i.e. the importance of the connected nodes (Hansen et al., 2020). Nodes with high eigenvector centrality have many connections to other highly connected nodes, indicating that they play a central role in the network. The node size is used to represent eigenvector centrality to communicate the relative importance of different nodes in the graph.

3. RESULTS

Using the method described in section two, three graphs were created - one for each similarity measure. Before applying the local filtering procedure, the RMSD between each pair of graphs was calculated. The RMSD between the graph generated using the AJC and the graph generated using the JC was calculated to be 0.18. Additionally, the RMSD between the AJC and the CS was determined to be 0.15. Furthermore, a comparison of the RMSD between the JC and the CS revealed a value of 0.04. These results indicate that while all similarity measures demonstrate minimal variations, the Jaccard coefficient and the cosine similarity exhibit a notably small difference in terms of the relationships they depict between the keywords.

3.1. KEYWORD STATISTIC

A total of 235 keywords were generated based on the variable encodings. The distribution of the number of keywords per accident can be seen in *Fig. 2*. On average 23 keywords are assigned per accident, with a minimum value of 4 and a maximum value of 32. While the number of keywords per accident is distributed very evenly around the mean with a standard deviation of 2.8, in *Fig. 3* it can be seen many keywords occur in only very few cases, but at the same time, few keywords are mentioned in very many cases. This effect is not surprising, since accidents share many characteristics by their similar nature and the number of possible specifications for some variables is small (e.g. an accident can either be a single or a multi-vehicle accident). At the same time, it also shows that accidents do differ in their details and that an analysis of these is important for accident prevention.

Fig. 2: Histogram showing the keywords assigned per accident.

Fig. 3: Distribution of the term frequency of keywords. It indicates how often the term (keyword) occurs in the sets of keywords.

3.2. NETWORK GRAPH

The following visualisation shows the layout of the three network graphs after the local filtering procedure has been performed.

Fig. 4: Overview of the graph layouts resulting from the calculation methods for the edge weight. From left to right: Jaccard similarity coefficient, adapted Jaccard similarity coefficient, and cosine similarity.

It can be seen that the graphs have dissimilar layouts. Due to the non-identical edge weights, different connections are kept in the filtering process. *Fig. 5* shows a section from all three graphs of the environment for the keyword "accidents in stationary traffic", which emerged from the coding of the single-digit accident type (Statistisches Bundesamt (Destatis), 2022). Even though the arrangement of the surrounding keywords is different, the cluster is present in all three graphs.

Fig. 5: Representation of a cluster that has formed in the same way in all three graphs.

In contrast, different constellations have formed around the keyword "alcohol". Since the RMSD between the unfiltered JC and CS graph is comparatively low, the nodes in close proximity to "alcohol" are very similar, whereas in graph AJC only a connection between the keywords "night" and "sporadic vehicles" can be detected.

Comparison to descriptive methods

Keyword: "Alcohol"

In the following, for the keyword "alcohol", it is checked whether the existing and visually quickly detectable connections are also found in the accident data using explorative statistical methods. The descriptive analysis is performed on the same GIDAS subsample that was used to generate the network graphs.

Graphs J and CS demonstrate a direct link between the keyword "alcohol" and the keyword "Ability to drive", which belongs to the category of main causes of accidents. By comparing the proportions of the accident cause between incidents with and without alcohol influence, it can be observed that accidents influenced by alcohol exhibit a clearly higher proportion of the accident cause "Ability to drive" – 21.9 % compared to 3.2 % (cf. Fig. 6).

Influence of alcohol	Main accident cause													
	Ability to drive	Behavior towards pedestrians	Distance	Driving alongside each other	Improper behavior of pedestrians	other	Overtaking	Passing	Right of way	Speed	Stationary traffic	Technical defects	Turning, reversing	Use of Road
yes	21,88%	2,30%	1,34%	0,19%	6,53%	35,12%	0,96%	0,19%	4,61%	14,97%	0,19%	0,58%	6,33%	4,80%
no	3,17%	4,74%	6,09%	1,35%	5,40%	23,25%	3,17%	0,33%	19,35%	8,99%	1,43%	0,65%	19,17%	2,89%

Fig. 6: Distribution of the main accident cause

Furthermore, in both graphs, a connection to the keyword "single-vehicle accident" can be seen. The connection seems plausible insofar as about 21% of the accidents in the data set are single-vehicle accidents. In the case of accidents involving alcohol, this proportion rises to 55 % (cf. Fig. 7). A possible conclusion from the perspective of active vehicle safety would be to address such accidents through an alcohol ignition interlock or improved ESC.

Fig. 7: Distribution of single vs. multi-vehicle accidents.

Analogously, the connection to the keyword "driving accident" (which belongs to the superordinate category of the accident type) can be confirmed in the descriptive analysis. While this category of accident type accounts for just under 17 % of all accidents, the proportion of accidents involving alcohol is just over 50 % (cf. Fig. 8).

Influence of alcohol	accident type						
	Collision in longitudinal traffic	Collision with stationary traffic	driving accident	Entering/crossing collision	Other collision	Pedestrian crossing street	Turning collision
yes	14,40%	5,18%	50,48%	8,06%	7,87%	8,06%	5,95%
no	20,53%	4,66%	16,85%	24,39%	8,74%	7,66%	17,18%

Fig. 8: Distribution of the category of the accident type (single-digit accident type)

Additionally, the link between e-scooters and other small electric vehicles and alcohol is also reflected in the CS graph. Although the sample of accidents involving these vehicles in the GIDAS database is still relatively small due to the recent implementation of the Personal Light Electric Vehicle Regulation in June 2019, the data suggests a high incidence of alcohol involvement in accidents involving these vehicles, with 38 % (5 out of 13) of the accidents being influenced by alcohol. Another connection shown by the CS graph is to the keyword "night", which results from the variable describing the time of day. Here, as well, a comparison of accidents with and without alcohol influence shows that accidents with an influence of alcohol occur in a considerably higher proportion at night (cf. Fig. 9).

Influence of alcohol	Time of day		
	day	night	twilight
yes	36,85%	54,13%	9,02%
no	78,24%	15,62%	6,14%

Fig. 9: Distribution of the time of day

Lastly, a significance analysis was performed there the null hypotheses for each test stated that there is no significant difference in proportions between accidents with and without alcohol influence, while the alternative hypotheses stated that there is a significant difference. The analysis was carried out for the factors "main accident cause", "single vs. multi-vehicle accidents", "accident type" and "time of day", as a sufficiently high number of cases is available for these factors. At a fixed significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, the null hypothesis could be rejected in every case, indicating a significant relationship between alcohol and the specified factors.

Keyword: "Mirror(s)"

As depicted in Fig. 10 in the JC and CS graph a close connection between the keyword "School Bus" (belonging to the official definition of the kind of road user) and the keyword "mirror(s)" (belonging to the variables for technical defects) is drawn. Looking into the GIDAS data reveals

that only 6 accidents involving school buses are included in the GIDAS database. In one of these accidents, a technical defect of the mirrors was recorded. Given the already low number of accidents involving school buses, it would be presumptuous to link these accidents to defective mirrors. However, the connection derived from the graphs can be explained, as only two of the 111007 accidents involved defective mirrors. Thus, 50 % of all accidents with defective mirrors are accidents involving a school bus. Since both quantities are small to a very similar degree, the connection in both graphs is considered important.

In contrast, the AJC graph shows a connection between “mirror(s)” and the keywords “rural road” and “T-junction”. These connections are plausible since both accidents with technically defective mirrors occurred at T-junctions on rural roads. Since the number of accidents at T-intersections and on rural roads is much higher, the union of sets including the keyword combinations becomes very large, resulting in only a small edge weight in the JC graph (and also the CS graph, that according to the RSMD produces a quite similar outcome). At this point, it is apparent that the AJC weighting method evaluates the connection considering the mutual relationship between the keyword, because 100% of the accidents with defective mirrors occurred at T-intersections and on rural roads, so the relationship appears important from this perspective.

Fig. 10: Connection between "school bus" and "mirror(s)" in the JC and CS graphs, the AJC graph shows a connection between "mirrors(s)" and the keywords "t-junction" and "rural road".

4. DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to examine whether network graphs are a suitable tool to visualize relationships in accident data and identify connections that are not directly obvious. Therefore, a subsample of the July 2021 GIDAS accident database containing 11107 accidents was used to generate three network graphs based on keywords. A method was proposed to extract 235 keywords from the accident information and to link them in a graph. Three ways of calculating edge weights were presented and a filtering process was established to reduce the number of edges for clearer visualization. The keyword "alcohol" was used as an example to investigate whether the most concise connections are also reflected in the accident data.

4.1. INTERPRETATIONS

In the context of accident data analysis, network graphs are a valuable tool for mapping relationships between different contributing factors. The visual representation of these relationships, through the placement of strongly connected accident characteristics in close proximity to each other, allows for quick identification of potential relationships without the need for extensive data analysis. The results from the use of network graphs have been supported by established methods of data evaluation and have demonstrated their ability to generate plausible connections between different contributing factors to accidents.

The weighting method used to construct the network graphs can also influence the relationships revealed. This highlights the importance of careful consideration of the method used in creating the graphs, as well as the importance of ongoing evaluation and refinement of these methods to ensure their validity and reliability. The graphical representation of the relationships within an accident database enables the formulation of hypotheses relatively quickly, which can then be further tested and validated through established statistical methods.

4.2. LIMITATIONS

While the use of network graphs provides several advantages, it also has some limitations that must be taken into consideration. Firstly, according to Jacomy et al. (2014), the force-directed drawing has the specificity of placing each node based solely on the connections between nodes. As a result, the graph layout can vary depending on the initial state and the process of generating network graphs can get stuck in a local minimum. The coordinates of each point do not reflect any

specific variable and are not deterministic. This means that nodes, where the connection has the highest weight, do not necessarily need to be placed nearby or that the connection is relevant according to the overall accident figures. Finally, it is important to note that the result cannot be read as a Cartesian projection and that the position of a node cannot be interpreted on its own (Jacomy et al., 2014).

The study used a subsample of the variables available in the GIDAS Database, which could also impact the accuracy of the results. Adding more variables to the analysis could lead to a more comprehensive understanding of latent relationships in accident data but brings the challenge of not overloading the graph visually.

4.3. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the use of network graphs in the analysis of accident data has shown promise in providing a visual representation of the relationships between different contributing factors and has the potential to support the development of effective strategies for reducing the number of road accidents and fatalities. Also, the application of network graphs for uncovering latent relationships within data holds potential, but the interpretation of what is considered latent can be subject to individual variation. Based on the current analysis, further research in the use of network graphs to detect latent relationships in data could include the exploration of additional weighting methods, the expansion of the variable sample, and the examination of connections specifically between influencing factors and the outcome of accidents. These areas of investigation could help to further validate the usefulness of network graphs and provide insights into how these relationships can be better understood and utilized.

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